

Measurement of Molecular Areas of Cellulose from Different Sources by Surface Tension Method. Part II.

J. K. CHOWDHURY AND T. P. BARDHAN.

Since the last decade vigorous attempts are being made by several investigators to determine the molecular size of cellulose. The older conception that cellulose consisted of a large number of anhydroglucose units, as first represented by the formula of Tollens, was modified some years ago by Hess, Karrer, Pringsheim and others who maintained that not more than four anhydroglucose units united by main valency bonds to form the cellulose molecule. The X-ray investigation, at the time, seemed to support this view. Staudinger, however, was the first to maintain from extensive investigation of both synthetic and natural polymers that cellulose and similar substances consist of a very large number of anhydroglucose units united together to form a long chain thread-molecule whose length was about 1000 times the breadth or thickness. This view has since been corroborated by a large number of independent investigators working from different points of view. The improved method of X-ray investigation, hydrolysis of cellulose, the properties of the end-groups in the chain, all corroborate that cellulose is made up of a very large number of anhydroglucose units. There is, however, some essential difference as to the magnitude of the molecule and the number of anhydroglucose units that go to form the cellulose molecule. While Staudinger, as a result of his very careful viscosity measurements, maintains that cellulose molecule consists of some 750 anhydroglucose units, with molecular weight of about 120,000, other investigators, however, ascribe only 100-200 anhydroglucose units to the cellulose molecule. From X-ray investigations, Mark and Meyer (*Ber.*, 1928, 61, 593) conclude that two glucose units, each of which is twisted 180° from its predecessor, go to form cellobiose units, as proposed by Haworth and about 60 such cellobiose units (*i.e.*, 120 anhydroglucose units) go to form one cellulose molecule. Some 40-50 of such molecules associate with each other somewhat loosely to form a micelle which is arranged parallel to the fibre-axis in the case of cotton. This order of magnitude finds corroboration in the work of Haworth (*Nature*, 1932, 129, 365) who estimates tetramethylglucose obtained from the hydrolysis of methylated cellulose. This tetramethyl compound is evidently due to the non-reducing end-group of the open-chain. From this, the size of the molecule has been found to consist of about 120 anhydroglucose units. The other

reducing end-group has been oxidised by Bergmann and Macheimer (*Ber.*, 1930, **63**, 316) with hypoiodite solution and approximately the same order of magnitude has been obtained. This magnitude has also been corroborated by osmotic pressure measurements of cellulose solution by Buchner and Samwell (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1933, **29**, 32) and also by the ultra-centrifuge measurements by Stamm (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 3047). Recently Craeiner and Lansing (*Nature*, 1934, **133**, 870) report that ultra-centrifuge measurements indicate a magnitude of 370-1110 glucose units in the cellulose molecule.

In the following experiments, an attempt has been made to determine the approximate order of magnitude of cellulose molecule by means of a method which has not so far been applied to it. It has been found that the surface tension of viscose solution changes with time and gradually attains a constant value after some time. This fall of surface tension is due (*cf.* Rideal, "Surface Chemistry," p. 31) to the molecules of the solute moving towards the surface where the concentration becomes greater than the bulk concentration and a unimolecular surface film is formed.

In this laboratory Ghosh and Nath (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 1916) studied the variation of surface tension of solutions of some complex organic substances, and modified the ring method of Freundlich with a view to avoid breaking up of the surface and cause the least possible disturbance. In the experiments to be described, this modified method has been followed for measuring surface tension.

The size of the cellulose molecule has been determined on the assumption that a unimolecular layer of cellulose molecule exists on the surface. Hence A , the area in sq. cm. per g. mole. = $1/\tau$ where τ denotes excess concentration at surface and N , the Avogadro's number, τ can be calculated from the well known Gibb's equation

$$\tau = \frac{1}{RT} \frac{d\sigma}{d \log c}$$

and may be found experimentally from the inclination of the curve obtained by plotting log of different concentrations against minimum surface tension ($d\sigma$).

The apparatus and procedure described by Ghosh and Nath (*loc. cit.*) has been followed for the purpose of measuring the surface tension.

Surface tension of the solution = $\sigma \times w_2/w_1$ where σ denotes surface tension of water at the temperature of the experiment. w_2 denotes the

additional weight required to raise the basin from the surface of the solution while just touching, and w_1 , the additional weight required to raise the basin from the surface of pure water.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The solution of viscose was made by the method described in Part I (Chowdhury and Bardhan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 240), the only difference being that conductivity water was used in this case instead of distilled water. The glass vessels and the nickel basin were washed also with conductivity water and the basin was dried inside a desiccator containing strong sulphuric acid.

Surface tension was first measured about 5 minutes after the solution had been poured in the measuring vessel and then a series of readings were taken at an interval of about one hour. Tables I to III show the results obtained for the surface tension of pure water and of alkaline solutions of viscose determined at intervals t (in minutes) reckoned from the time at which the first observation was made. In the following tables t stands for time and σ for surface tension.

Variation of Surface Tension of Cotton-viscose Solution with Time at Different Concentrations at 20°.

TABLE I.

Composition of the solvent = 80% water, 4% of 16.91% NaOH soln. and 16% of 4.94% NaOH soln. Surface tension of water at 20° = 72.69 dynes/cm. Surface tension of the solvent at 20° = 55.67 dynes/cm.

Conc. = 0.002%.		Conc. = 0.004%.		Conc. = 0.006%.		Conc. = 0.01.		Conc. = 0.02%.	
t .	σ .	t .	σ .	t .	σ .	t .	σ .	t .	σ .
0	53.56	0	53.12	0	53.04	0	52.85	0	52.52
32	50.85	30	50.75	35	50.41	30	50.42	45	49.93
60	49.74	100	49.21	91	49.25	105	48.87	115	48.45
125	49.25	165	49.03	165	48.92	185	48.51	210	48.12
200	49.13	245	48.85	220	48.53	230	48.32	280	47.84
285	48.82	320	48.63	290	48.48	305	48.25	345	47.84
342	48.82	375	48.63	347	48.48	374	48.25	402	47.84
409	48.82	417	48.63	402	48.48	409	48.25		

MEASUREMENT OF MOLECULAR AREAS OF CELLULOSE 297

Conc. = 0.04%		Conc. = 0.06%		Conc. = 0.1%		Conc. = 0.14%		Conc. = 0.2%	
t.	σ .	t.	σ .	t.	σ .	t.	σ .	t.	σ .
0	52.15	0	51.50	0	50.28	0	49.42	0	47.82
42	49.13	35	48.75	50	47.23	35	46.75	25	45.75
95	47.75	105	46.91	125	45.75	105	44.92	85	43.25
170	47.42	192	46.45	194	45.22	155	44.38	135	42.51
317	47.01	310	46.15	245	45.01	230	43.82	215	41.74
365	47.01	365	46.15	315	44.74	312	43.51	337	41.05
404	47.01	413	46.15	385	44.74	363	43.51	385	41.05
						415	43.51	425	41.05

Variation of Surface Tension of Jute-viscose Solution with Time at Different Concentrations at 20°.

TABLE II.

Composition and surface tension of solvent—same as before.

Conc. = 0.002%		Conc. = 0.004%		Conc. = 0.006%		Conc. = 0.01%		Conc. = 0.02%	
0	55.12	0	54.85	0	54.74	0	54.46	0	53.85
30	53.64	35	53.15	35	52.84	30	52.51	30	51.92
90	52.75	105	52.21	95	52.12	80	51.78	105	50.87
162	52.43	170	51.93	155	51.83	154	51.45	195	50.52
235	52.25	264	51.84	245	51.52	255	51.24	285	50.22
315	52.25	320	51.84	307	51.52	312	51.18	347	50.32
375	52.25	385	51.84	385	51.52	367	51.18	405	50.32
						403	51.18		

Conc. = 0.04%		Conc. = 0.06%		Conc. = 0.1%		Conc. = 0.14%		Conc. = 0.2%	
0	53.13	0	52.66	0	51.87	0	50.23	0	49.17
35	50.90	30	50.50	34	49.83	35	48.41	30	47.15
105	50.18	85	49.38	95	48.52	96	47.12	94	45.30
205	49.65	195	48.71	155	47.95	185	46.21	192	43.51
305	49.28	300	48.42	235	47.42	295	45.72	313	43.15
372	49.28	352	48.42	312	47.03	362	45.72	357	43.15
413	49.28	402	48.42	370	47.02	423	45.72	415	43.15
				415	47.03				

Variation of Surface Tension of Bamboo-viscose Solution with Time at Different Concentrations at 20°.

TABLE III.

Composition and surface tension of the solvent—same as before.

Conc. = 0.006%.		Conc. = 0.01%.		Conc. = 0.02%.		Conc. = 0.04%.	
<i>t.</i>	σ .	<i>t.</i>	σ .	<i>t.</i>	σ .	<i>t.</i>	σ .
0	55.42	0	55.23	0	54.97	0	54.24
30	54.25	35	54.82	30	53.45	35	52.21
95	53.86	105	53.25	94	52.48	115	51.32
165	53.75	195	53.21	185	51.91	195	50.95
205	53.72	270	52.74	280	51.58	290	50.53
270	53.52	325	52.74	347	51.58	364	50.53
345	53.52	397	52.74	405	51.58	424	50.53
402	53.52						

Conc. = 0.06%.		Conc. = 0.1%		Conc. = 0.14%		Conc. = 0.2%	
<i>t.</i>	σ .	<i>t.</i>	σ .	<i>t.</i>	σ .	<i>t.</i>	σ .
0	53.18	0	52.85	0	51.44	0	49.27
30	51.68	45	50.32	40	49.15	35	46.85
105	50.45	130	49.61	115	48.34	94	45.74
200	50.21	215	48.92	194	47.73	207	45.31
275	49.95	312	48.42	291	47.35	318	44.78
365	49.95	378	48.42	368	47.35	385	44.78
417	49.95	435	48.42	434	47.35	443	49.78

DISCUSSION.

Variation of Surface Tension with Time.

It will be seen from Fig. 1 that the variation of surface tension with time is fairly regular, unlike the behaviour of the colloidal dyestuff solution as observed by Ghosh and Nath (*loc. cit.*). Here the surface tension falls steadily though rapidly during the first 2 hours attaining a constant value after some 5 or 6 hours. The limiting surface tension can, therefore, be determined experimentally and need not be found by extrapolation from the curve,

FIG. 1.

Viscose in NaOH soln. at 20°.

1-3 refer respectively to 0.01% jute, 0.006% cotton and 0.14% bamboo cellulose.

FIG. 2.

Viscose in NaOH soln. at 20°.

1-3 refer respectively to bamboo, jute and cotton cellulose.

Variation of Surface Tension with Concentration.

The values of the limiting surface tension of solutions of different concentrations are represented graphically in Fig. 2. It will be found that in very dilute solution the curve tends to become a straight line but the region of the concentrations in which such simple relationship of surface tension with concentrations is observed, is not, however, very great, as the curves bend rather quickly above the concentration 0.0081%, 0.01% and 0.24% in the case of cotton, jute and bamboo respectively. Attempts to correlate concentration and surface tension must, therefore, be limited to very low concentration. Gibb's equation is also applicable to solutions of high dilutions only, as the molecules are free to move only in very dilute solutions, where gas-laws are applicable. The molecular size of cellulose, particularly that of cotton cellulose, introduces, however, some complexities as such large molecules even in dilute solutions can not be absolutely without action on one another, though such action is naturally reduced to a minimum at very great dilutions. The values of τ are, therefore, determined from the inclinations of the above curves in high dilutions only. The molecular areas in sq. Å, as calculated from curve in Fig. 2, are given in Table IV. The standard celluloses from cotton, jute and bamboo, as used in viscosity measurements, were used in these experiments also. Calculation is based on ash and moisture free cellulose.

TABLE IV.

Substance.	$d\sigma/d \log c$.	Molecular area.
Cotton cellulose	0.49/0.7	571 sq. Å.
Jute cellulose	1.2/0.79	263.1
Bamboo cellulose	4.05/1.17	129.5

$$\tau = \frac{1}{RT} \cdot \frac{d\sigma}{d \log c} \text{ and } a = \text{mol. area} = \frac{1}{\tau N} = \frac{RT}{N} \cdot \frac{d \log c}{d\sigma} \text{ sq. cm}$$

$$= \frac{8.252 \times 10^7 \times 293}{6.05 \times 10^{23}} \times \frac{0.7}{0.49} \times \frac{1}{10^{-16}} \text{ sq. Å} = 571 \text{ sq. Å}$$

It may be argued that the molecular area as calculated above, represents the area not of molecules but of micelle, as the molecules of cellulose might be associated with one another to form micelles in solution. Staudinger has, however, shown that cellulose in dilute solution forms molecule-colloids and does not tend to form micelles. This view has also been corroborated by X-ray investigation and also by N. K. Adam (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1933, 29, 105) who found in his spreading experiments that cellulose forms a monomolecular film, the thickness of which does not exceed that of an ordinary molecule. He also finds that the cellulose molecules lie absolutely flat on the water surface. It is, therefore, reasonable to assume that the films formed on the surface of the solutions investigated in this work, are also unimolecular in nature and the molecules lie flat on the surface. The area, as calculated, above, would, therefore, represent the average molecular size, provided the film on the surface is really unimolecular like the film investigated by Adam.

It is thus evident that the number of anhydroglucose groups in cellulose from different sources is not same and the degree of polymerisation varies according to the source from which cellulose is obtained. This view is also supported by the viscosity experiments as described in the previous part (*loc. cit.*).